

DIFFERENT ACCOUNTS REGARDING DETERMINERS

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Abstract

The purpose of this article the classification of determiners in Japanese taking into consideration different accounts from a number of authors that deal with this subject. As we know, determiners are important in Japanese since they are bearers of definiteness and can help obtain definite Noun Phrases in the absence of articles. For this reason, we will resort only to the lexical classification of determiners in Japanese. These are a highly structured lexeme which include classifiers, quantifiers and particles together to form a homogenous grammatical class. There is considerable disagreement as to whether these particles head the constituents they appear in. Some linguists say they always head them, making the phrases postpositional phrases (Gunji, 1987; Siegel, 1998), while some say they sometimes do, making a distinction between noun phrases and postpositional phrases.

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7.1.1. Shibatani’s (2005) Analysis of Japanese Determiners

Shibatani (2005) departs from previous researchers in that he assigns Japanese determiners class homogeneity, meaning that, despite their variation in terms of syntax and semantics, they form a class with particular properties. It must be observed that Japanese nouns are devoid of plural markers. However,

Shibatani states that Number plays the most decisive role in forming determiners in Japanese, and, at the same time, it is the condition for conveying definiteness (pp.410). He generally classifies determiners in Japanese in three groups: classifiers, quantifiers and particles.

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The stark contrast with English is evident. This is because one major difference is in word order: in Japanese, dependents normally precede their heads. For example, in a clause the verb is final (SOV): [inu-ga]S [hone-o]O [tabeta]V “the dog ate a bone”. (Fukui, 2021:32). The relation between nouns and verbs is shown by postpositional particles. There is considerable disagreement as to whether these particles

head the constituents they appear in. Some linguists say they always head them, making the phrases postpositional phrases (Gunji, 1987; Siegel, 1998), while some say they sometimes do, making a distinction between noun phrases and postpositional phrases (Tsujiimura, 1996; Hawkins, 1994).

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Japanese Postpositions (Ono, 1996)

Type (Number)	Examples
case-markers (3)	-ga “nominative”, -o “accusative”, -ni “dative”
semantic-markers (8)	-ni “locative/goal”, -e “locative-goal”, -de “locative/instrumental”, -to “committative”, -kara “source”, -made “goal”, -yori “source/comparative”, -no “adnominal”
adverbial-markers (10)	-wa “topic”, -mo “emphatic”, -nado “such as”, -dake “only”, -made “even”, -bakari “only”, -sae “even”, -demo “even”, -shika “only”, -sura “even”

Japanese noun phrases show no number contrast. There is no morphological or syntactic distinction between singular and plural, or countable and

uncountable. For this reason, Shibatani argues that in Japanese noun phrases require the presence of a determiner in order to express Number. Fukui (1995)

goes even further and argues that Japanese does not have the syntactic function of specifier. He then argues that Japanese sentences can have multiple subjects, and that Japanese noun phrases can have more than one determiner, unlike English. Thus, Japanese has no functional categories equivalent to English subjects or specifiers. In fact, there is no syntactic equivalent to English determiners, but the semantic equivalents to the English determiners are always omissible and there may be more than one. Some examples are given in (146), where possessive phrases and determinatives co-occur (Bond, 2001:31):

- (146) a. *Watashi-no kono hon*
Pron.I, NOM., Pron.This, N.Book
 This book of mine. (lit. my this book)
- b. *Tarou no kinou no hanashi*
N.Tarou, NOM., Adv.Yesterday, NOM., N.Story
 The story [Tarou gave/about Tarou] yesterday.

Another difference is with the demonstratives themselves. Where English has only two lexemes *this/these* “proximal” and *that/those* “distal”; Japanese has a three-way distinction between *kore* “proximal”, *sore* “medial” and *are* “distal”. There is also a related interrogative: *dore* “which/what”. English uses the same form for both determiners and demonstrative pronouns, but in Japanese, the preceding forms are used

only as demonstrative pronouns. The adnominal forms are derived by replacing *re* with *no*: *kono* “this”, *sono* “that medial”, *ano* “thatdistal”, *dono* “which” or with *nna*: e.g., *konna* “this kind of” or lengthening the first vowel followed by *yuu*: e.g., *kouyuu* “this kind of” (Shibatani, 2005:192)

147.a. *Sono* tookoo-ni nan-byaku-toiuu komento-ga tsuita.

Pron.Dem.That,N.Post,Prep.To,Num.One Hundred,N.Comment-NOM,V.PAST.Provide
 ‘That post got hundreds of comments.’

b. *Ano* byooin-ga san-nin-no kangohu-o sagasiteiru (koto)

That hospital-Nom three-CL no nurse-Acc looking for-Asp fact

‘That hospital is looking for three nurses’

Numeral classifiers are organized into a grammatical system that reflects how speakers categorize objects that they count or quantify. Classifiers usually occur adjacent to quantity expressions including numbers. The selection of numeral classifiers is determined by the inherent semantic features of the noun being quantified or counted (Shibatani, 2006:181). These properties are illustrated below:

148.

Num.Five,CLASS.,GEN,N.Flower
Adv.Many, GEN.,N.Flower
 ‘Five flowers’
 ‘A lot of flowers’

Shibatani (2005:201), proposes a number of syntactic and semantic properties that characterize Japanese in terms of countability. As a matter of fact, it results that Nominals in classifier languages like Japanese have the following properties:

a. Countability cannot be expressed independently through the employment of numerals alone, but they must be adjoined to a highly specified classifier which, together with the numeral, form a Nominal Phrase, meaning that it behaves like a nominal adjective:

149. *ichi-*(rin)-no- hana*
. Num.One,CLASS,GEN.,N.Flower
 „One Flower”

b. There are no plurality markers on nouns, with a few exceptions like *-tachi*, or *-gata*, which act like suffixes and are lexical in nature (e.g. the same noun as (3) is used in the following examples below). Moreover, bare nouns can denote kinds (Krifka 1995):

150. *go-rin-no hana*
 151. *takusan-no hana*

7.1.1.1. Ono’s (1996) Classification of Japanese Determiners

Unlike Shibatani, Ono (1996) treats determiners as part of a heterogeneous class of elements that have no syntactic structure and which are generally employed into language by means of convention, rather than semantics. The most striking feature of his analysis represents the fact that he introduces modifiers and adjuncts together with determiners (in Shibatani’s terms), and considers all these constructions as being part of a class of elements that convey definiteness in Japanese.

152. The Definite Items of a Japanese Noun Phrase according to Ono (1996)

Quantifiers	Determiners	PPs.	Modifiers	Heads	Complements
Zenbu(all)	Ano(that), kono(this),	Genitive	-Adjectives	- Nouns -	-some adj.
Ryohou(both)	sonna(such),	Constructions	- Nouns	Clauses	- NGs
Sonoyouna/ Nanno (such)	jibun(self), washino(my),	+ NO, Kara... Yoroppa no			- PGs
Hanbun(half)	mai(every),	Hito(European),			- Clauses
gofunnoni	Pers.Pron+NO	Ajia kara			
sukoshi(little)	sorezore(each),	hito(Asian),			
oukuno(little)	doreka/dochira(which)	Amerika noni deta hito(American), youna etc,			

Another striking feature is that he introduces nominalizations as an important definite mechanism, in other words, as a determiner. While for Shibatani (2005), this would mean an instance of a postpositional particle „no”, which he mentions as being part of a closed class of elements that form determiners in Japanese. It allows the formation of NPs by means of nominalization, which is considered a morphosyntactic process in Ono (1996). This is achieved by means of particles, suffixes, conversion etc. It brings forth derivative nouns by operating on the different grammatical classes involving the process of derivation as well as that of operating on nominal constituents and nominal clauses (Ono, 1996:50-81).

In addition to the previous determiners, there are other constructions in Japanese related to definiteness. Another feature of the analysis provided by Ono (1996) is that he emphasizes the employment of the generic noun *koto* as a determiner. He argues that the formal noun *koto* “thing” can be used as a determiner to mark definiteness in noun phrases of the form *NP-no koto*. More specifically, he claims that noun phrases headed by *koto* that are the complement of intentional or emotional predicates are definite, unless they are quantified. Demonstratives are an additional part of this. He considers three cases: un-quantified common nouns (153.a), proper nouns or nouns modified by a demonstrative (153b) and quantified nouns (153c). They can be contrasted to (153d), which can be used if there is a certain unknown professor (indefinite), a familiar professor (definite) or if Hiromi likes professors in general (generic). The generic reading is the most common interpretation:

153. a. Hiromi-wa kyoju-no-koto-ga suki-da.
N.Hiromi-TOP, N.Professor-ADN-KOTO-NOM, V.Pres.Like-be
 Hiromi likes the professor.
- b. Hiromi-wa Nagao-no-koto-ga suki-da.
N.Hiromi-TOP, N.Nagao-ADN-KOTO-NOM, V.Pres.Like-be
 Hiromi likes Nagao.
- c. Hiromi-wa taitei-no — kyōdō-no-koto-ga suki-da.
N.Hiromi-TOP, Adv.Most-ADM, N.Professor-ADN-KOTO-NOM, V.Pres.Like-be
 Hiromi likes most professors.
- d. Hiromi-wa kyoju-ga suki-da.
N.Hiromi-TOP, N.Professor-NOM, V.Pres.Like-be
 Hiromi likes a/the professor.

Hiromi likes professors.

7.4. Conclusions of this Section

The constituents of the Japanese NPs are highly similar to those in any European language, but they depart from their counterparts in that definiteness can be triggered by some of these constituents like, to say, adjuncts or relative clauses. This is mostly due to the existence of nominalization in Japanese, as shown in table 42, where all of the definite NPs contain modifiers introduced by the nominalizing particle NO. This is further demonstrated by examples below, extracted from Niwa (2013:29):

167. a. 3- nen- B- gumi- no dareka- wa Michiko- no koto- ga suki- rashī.

3rd year class B- GEN someone- TOP Michiko- GEN thing- NOM like- seems

Someone in the third year₁ class B₂ seems to like Michiko.

b. Taian Shōji- no ōku- no shain- tachi- wa, 5- ji- ni naru- to suguni kaeru

Taian Trading Company- GEN many- GEN staff- PL- TOP 5 pm- DAT

turn- COMP soon go Many of the staff at Taian Trading Company go home right after it turns 5pm

These two instances are coined by Niwa to be topic noun phrases and they include modifiers and nominalizers. What sets them apart from the other sentences we analyzed above is that there is hierarchy of NPs within the phrase which allows for the determination of definiteness within the clause. When an element or the subset of a certain object A is B, Niwa calls A the “upper-class set” of B. *3-nen-Bgumi-no seito-tachi* (the students of third-year class B) is the upper-class set for which *3-nen-B-gumi-no dareka* (someone in third-year class B) is a subset and *Taian-Shōji-no shain-tachi* (the staff at Taian Trading Company) is the upper-class set of *Taian-Shōji-no ōku-no shain-tachi* (many of the staff at Taian Trading Company). The noun phrases expressing these upper-class sets belong respectively to (ii) for *Taian-Shōji-no shain-tachi* (the staff at Taian Trading Company) and to the (iii) for *3-nen-B-gumi-no seito-tachi* (the students of third-year class B). According to Niwa, the reason why (32)b and (33)b are able to function as topic noun phrases regardless of the fact that they are indefinite noun phrases is because the upper-class set directly above it is a *definite noun phrase*. The same happens with relative clauses (Niwa, 2013:30)

168. *Wārudokappu- no kaisai- chū* ōku- no hito- tachi- wa terebi- ni kugizuke- datta. *World Cup- GEN held- during many GEN person- PL- TOP*

televisionDAT riveted- COP- PAST Many people were riveted to the TV during the World Cup.

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